

1 **Therapeutic targeting in androgen receptor-positive triple negative breast cancer (AR+ TNBC):**
2 **PPP1R37.**

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7 Triple negative breast cancer is defined by combined lack of expression of the hormone receptors *ESR1*,
8 *PGR* and the growth factor receptor *HER2*; thus, endocrine therapy and trastuzumab are generally not
9 considered viable therapies for patients with TNBC (1-5). We recently utilized whole transcriptome
10 technologies to define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+
11 breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Measuring total transcription with
12 RNA-sequencing and microarray in cancer based on quantitative expression of a defined biomarker or the
13 normal tissues from which they are derived enables rational design and development of novel
14 chemotherapies with optimized therapeutic index (9). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies
15 (10, 11) to measure total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with androgen receptor-positive
16 TNBC. We describe a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and differentially expressed in TNBCs that
17 express the androgen receptor, *PPP1R37*, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical management
18 of the primary tumor in AR+ TNBC.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lung, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in primary tumors of the humans with triple negative breast cancers that express the androgen receptor to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the AR+ TNBC transcriptome in humans: a therapeutic target that is differentially expressed based on expression of the androgen receptor, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy in TNBC: PPP1R37.

Results

Figure 1: PPP1R37 is differentially expressed in the primary tumors of humans with AR+ TNBC.

- I. Primary tumors from humans with AR- and AR+ TNBC.

n=7 AR- TNBC (human)
n=28 AR+ TNBC (human)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2843520	3.30E-02	0.405	-2.131839	-0.8637214	68.88	PPP1R37	1656/19188	91.4

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors in humans with AR- and AR+ TNBC, we discovered differential expression of protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 37, encoded by *PPP1R37* in TNBC (**Chart 1**). The expression of PPP1R37 changed more than 90% of the human AR+ TNBC transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,188 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PPP1R37 messenger RNA in androgen receptor-positive triple negative breast cancer (AR+ TNBC) indicating up-regulation of PPP1R37 during transformation in AR+ TNBC.

1 II. Primary tumor cells from humans with AR+ and AR- TNBC.

2 $n=5$ AR- TNBC (human)

3 $n=6$ AR+ TNBC (human)

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ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
6134	1.63E-02	-2.7741196	-3.04135	-0.8950485	PPP1R37	2185/45015	95.1

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6 Through measurement of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with AR+ TNBC as
7 compared to AR- TNBC, we validated differential expression of PPP1R37 in AR+ TNBC in humans (**Chart**
8 **2**). The expression of PPP1R37 here changed more than 95% of the AR+ TNBC transcriptome when
9 considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 45,015 transcripts ("Rank").
Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PPP1R37 messenger RNA in the primary
tumors of humans with AR+ TNBC, indicating up-regulation of PPP1R37 during transformation in AR+
TNBC.

10 Thus, differential and increased expression of PPP1R37 defines the tumor transcriptome in human
11 AR+ TNBC.

12 **Discussion**

13 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
14 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
15 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of PPP1R37, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be tested for
16 efficacy in patients with AR+ TNBC who have failed previous treatment, with the goal of identifying the
17 most effective first-line chemotherapy regimens for humans with AR+ TNBC, as well as for patients with
18 disease recurrence at the primary site. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with
19 chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at
20 anaphase, and target *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is
21 most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (12).

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Methods

We utilized GSE244271 and GSE38959 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in AR- and AR+ TNBC using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.